

Ubaydullayeva Gulshoda

Raximova Muyassar

Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health

named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

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HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AND ITS SEVEN RULES

Annotation: *This article is about a healthy lifestyle, which is one of the most pressing issues today.*

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A healthy lifestyle means following a daily routine, exercising, eating a full and quality diet, following good hygiene, and avoiding bad habits, he said. - Physical activity naturally stimulates the body. Therefore, energetic and restless people are always alert, strong, energetic and courageous even in old age. Unfortunately, in the current context of urbanization, there is a significant decrease in physical activity among the general public and our youth. Therefore, the formation of a healthy lifestyle in society, the mass struggle against inactivity, the protection of high physical and mental performance of people, the involvement of the general population, especially young people in sports are becoming increasingly important.

- What are the negative consequences of an unhealthy lifestyle?

- Unhealthy lifestyles and physical inactivity are leading causes of disability and premature death worldwide due to non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular disease, stroke, malignant tumors, chronic inflammation of the respiratory system, and diabetes. According to the World Health Organization, the problem of overweight and obesity has been on the rise in the world over the past few decades. In 2015, non-communicable diseases claimed the lives of 40 million people, accounting for 70% of all deaths worldwide. What is the situation in Uzbekistan in this regard? - In our country, non-communicable diseases cause 78% of all deaths every year. In 2017, circulatory system diseases, including coronary heart disease, arterial hypertension and its complications (myocardial infarction, stroke, etc.) ranked first in the structure of standardized causes of death by gender and age (69%). They were followed by malignant tumors (8%), diabetes (3%) and respiratory diseases (3%). In 2014-2015, a study conducted by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan in collaboration with the World Health Organization among the population aged 18-64 showed negative results. In particular, two-thirds of the population (67%) do not eat enough vegetables and fruits (less than 400 grams per day), and half are overweight (body mass index ≥ 25 kg / m²). One in five of our adult compatriots is obese (body mass index ≥ 30 kg / m²). Elevated levels of cholesterol in the blood were reported in 46% of the population. 42% of men and 1.5% of women smoke. Nearly one-third of the population reported high blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$ mm Hg). One-fifth of people aged

40-64 have a 30-year risk of developing cardiovascular disease over a ten-year period. The average daily salt intake of humans is 14.9 grams, which is three times the recommended level (less than 5 grams per day). The World Health Organization estimates that the economic damage caused by noncommunicable diseases in 2016 was about 9.3 trillion soums, or 4.7 percent of the country's gross domestic product. Maintaining a healthy lifestyle can help prevent many problems. We come across this topic a lot today. What are the basic rules of a healthy lifestyle that seem difficult at first glance, require a lot of strength, patience and will, time and conditions? How can you maintain a healthy lifestyle today, when there is no easier task than giving advice to others? The following are the 7 Most Important Rules of a Healthy Lifestyle.

1. Sport. Sport is one of the main conditions for a healthy life for the rest of our lives. He does not choose age, place, or even circumstances. It has many forms, shapes and methods. There are types of yoga, pilates, walking, jogging, horizontal bar pull-ups, jogging, dancing, rafting, bodybuilding, gymnastics, football and so on. Choose what you want, just be physically active. If you exercise 30-60 minutes a day, not every day, it will be enough to stay healthy. You need to sit less and move more. If your profession requires you to sit down, take a break of at least 5 minutes every hour, during which time do a variety of light exercises and write down the shoulders, waist and legs.

2. Eat right. Include more natural foods in your diet - fruits and vegetables, foods rich in vitamins and minerals. Fruits and vegetables, bread and cereals make up 65 percent of the diet, meat and dairy products 30 percent, and sweets and fats 5 percent. Foods should be as fresh and seasonal as possible. Plants should be given more space in spring and summer, and more protein and fat in winter. Drink about 2 liters of water every day. Avoid fast food, fizzy drinks, semi-finished products, chips and cereals, and many other foods that are artificially flavored, colored, and shaped. Avoid mixing different foods when eating. Fruits should be consumed half an hour before meals, tea and drinks 1-2 hours later. After 7pm, only a few apples are allowed to be eaten.

3. Harmful habits. Open the way to a healthy lifestyle by giving up tobacco and alcohol, which are the main enemies of our body, and various harmful habits (you know them well). Every cigarette you don't smoke, every glass of vodka you don't drink is an important step towards a healthier life.

4. Agenda. Stick to your schedule. First of all - 8 hours of sleep! Second, get into the habit of sleeping at the same time of day and waking up at the same time! Sleep disorders can gradually damage a person's psyche, emotions, and mood, leading to the development of various chronic, serious illnesses.

5. Positive mood. Another important rule of a healthy lifestyle is a bright and positive mood! Enjoy life more, do not pay much attention to failures, failures, always find the strength to move forward and do not hold grudges, resentments, bad suspicions towards people, be forgiving, tolerant ling. Never be equal to the ignorant!

6. Fresh air. Always keep your home, room, and office clean, wipe them daily, open windows, and get fresh air. To be in good shape, you need to know how to breathe deeply

and properly. Walking in nature, opening windows for a while, or doing physical work in the garden or outdoors is not enough.

7. Personal hygiene. Of course, washing your hands before and after eating, brushing your teeth before going to bed and after eating, clean clothes, and generally adhering to cleanliness are the main conditions for a healthy lifestyle. Don't forget! A healthy lifestyle is the key to disease prevention and health. It is the key to the development of various aspects of man, to success. A person who follows the rules of a healthy lifestyle will have a place in the family, work community, society in general, learn to overcome various difficult situations, not to lose himself in the face of life's challenges. One more thing! The rules of a healthy lifestyle are mutually supportive, and it's impossible to have one without the other. By taking action now, without leaving them for tomorrow, we can take the first steps toward a healthier and happier life.

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